

Questionnaire for Lunar Base Site Selection Factor Evaluating

Note:

The purpose of this survey is to determine the relative weights among the factors influencing the selection of the site for a lunar research station. The survey is designed in the form of Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), where the importance of factors at the same level is pairwise compared. The measurement scale is divided into 9 levels, where the values 9, 7, 5, 3, 1 correspond to absolutely important, very important, important, slightly important, equally important, and 8, 6, 4, 2 indicate importance between adjacent levels. "-" is used to indicate more important on the left, "+" is used to indicate more important on the right, and 0 represents inability to judge.

- Q1 Level-1: Engineering vs. Resource utilization
- Q2 Level-1: Engineering vs. Geology
- Q3 Level-1: Engineering vs. Space environment
- Q4 Level-1: Resource utilization vs. Geology
- Q5 Level-1: Resource utilization vs. Space environment
- Q6 Level-1: Geology vs. Space environment
- Q7 Level-2: Slope vs. Roughness
- Q8 Level-2: Slope vs. Illumination
- Q9 Level-2: Slope vs. Earth visibility
- Q10 Level-2: Roughness vs. Illumination
- Q11 Level-2: Roughness vs. Earth visibility
- Q12 Level-2: Illumination vs. Earth visibility
- Q13 Level-2: Mineral abundance vs. Element abundance
- Q14 Level-2: Impact crater with central peak vs. Ejecta from SPA
- Q15 Level-2: Impact crater with central peak vs. Geological formation

- Q16** Level-2: Ejecta from SPA vs. Geological formation
- Q17** Level-2: Sky visibility vs. Optical maturity
- Q18** Level-3: Olivine abundance vs. Clinopyroxene abundance
- Q19** Level-3: Olivine abundance vs. Orthopyroxene abundance
- Q20** Level-3: Clinopyroxene abundance vs. Orthopyroxene abundance
- Q21** Level-3: Hydrogen abundance vs. Iron Oxide abundance
- Q22** Level-3: Hydrogen abundance vs. Titanium Oxide abundance
- Q23** Level-3: Iron Oxide abundance vs. Titanium Oxide abundance
- Q24** Level-3: Shallow fault vs. Impact fracture
- Q25** Level-3: Shallow fault vs. Lobate scarp
- Q26** Level-3: Impact fracture vs. Lobate scarp